

An On-Device Machine Learning Assisted System for Unobtrusive Cardiac Auscultation

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ABSTRACT

This paper uses on-device machine learning to present a microcontroller-based cardiac auscultation system for heart sound classification. Real-time analysis of heart sounds for the identification of abnormalities can prove important in early diagnosis of heart disease. However, this process of cardiac auscultation faces two important challenges, one of which is the form factor of the device that is being used for the auscultation/analysis and the other being poor classification performance due to the presence of environment noise in the recorded heart sound. This paper, therefore, develops a signal processing pipeline to extract three distinct two-dimensional features from a recorded heart sound and numerically analyses the effect of environment noise on them. Henceforth, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based classification layer is proposed to perform real-time analysis on heart sounds. The classifier is seen to achieve a peak accuracy of 91.2%, a precision of 91.2%, an F-1 score of 90.2%, with Youden's index of 0.847 and discriminant power of 2.980. This classification layer then forms the basis of development for a portable device that can perform real-time heart sound classification while consuming around 68.34 mW of power and is also impervious to environmental distortions.

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular Diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death globally. An estimated 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2019, representing about 32% of all global deaths [1]. Among these deaths, 85% are due to heart attack and stroke [2]. Most cardiovascular diseases can be prevented by addressing behavioural risk factors such as the use of tobacco, obesity due to an unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, and harmful use of alcohol [3]. It is, therefore, important to detect cardiovascular disease at an early stage so that management with counselling and the use of proper medication can begin at the earliest [4]. The primary way of

Figure 1: The various parts of PCG signal.[5]

identifying CVDs is by analysing heart sounds (HSs), which contain important acoustic information. HS also reflects an alteration in the acoustic signature following the emergence of pathological conditions [6]. These alterations provide an opportunity for the diagnosis of CVD at an early stage. The

blood flowing through the heart chambers during the cardiac cycle are responsible for generating the HSs, these sounds are also referred to as Phonocardiogram (PCG) signals [7] which can be detected during the auscultation process using a standard stethoscope [8]. Two key sounds can be observed during the cardiac cycle. S1 (lub) occurs at systolic start when tricuspid and mitral valves close [9]. S2 (dub) happens at diastolic onset when aortic and pulmonary valves close. S1 has a low pitch and longer duration, while S2 has a higher pitch and shorter duration. In normal conditions, S1-S2 duration is shorter than S2-S1. Figure 1 shows a typical PCG labeled ECG signal. A significant amount of research has been performed in the area of automatic heart sound analysis for the detection of CVD [10] including the development of medical screening devices like digital stethoscopes with murmur analysis algorithms [11]. Similar to the stated auscultation devices, the 2016 Physionet/CinC Challenge dataset [12] along with various other publicly available datasets [13] and the advent of efficient classification algorithms have also accelerated the progress of research in this area.

These classification algorithms have been studied for a variegated range of input features such as spectral, statistical, and Mel frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) [14, 15]. Time-frequency-based features including MFCC and Mel Spectrograms are most commonly used in recent studies. However, the majority of the work in [9, 16] have been studied/implemented considering a full-fledged desktop computer in mind where even in some cases a Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) has been used to speed up the training or inference time. The major limitation of the previous approaches is that, while they discussed the effect of various Time-frequency based input features but the use of proprietary development frameworks and a full-fledged

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desktop restricts the portability of the application. The advent of TinyML [17, 18] and the ability to run Deep Neural Networks (DNN) on microcontrollers [19] have opened a world of possibilities of applications that are low-powered and require intelligence on the edge. This paper, therefore, aims to develop an unobtrusive HS auscultation device to address the aforesaid problem. In this paper, Section 1 introduces the work. The signal processing pipeline and the mathematical description of the extracted features from heart sound data are given in Section 2. Section 3 talks about the classifier architecture in 3.1 sub-section, subsequent model performance parameters in 3.2, and section 3.4 which postulates the proposed embedded systems for heart sound auscultation. This is followed by section 4 which discusses the performance metrics. Finally, section 5 concludes the work.

2. System overview and data collection

In the case of heart sounds the major sources of signal degradation are: (i) the variability due to stethoscopes/sensor [20] affecting the PCG as a convolutional degradation (channel distortion), and (ii) the effect of additive noise (e.g., from the environment or the patient). The schematic model of a

Figure 2: Schematic showing the sources of additive noise during cardiac auscultation.

stethoscope retrofitted with a MEMS microphone with the aforesaid effects is shown in Fig. 2, this assumes the original PCG signal $e[t]$ with an uncorrelated noise component $n[t]$ being processed through a time-convolution operation due to the MEMS microphone's impulse response $h[t]$.

2.1. Heart sound data collection

The HS audio signal is recorded using an analogue MEMS Microphone by Adafruit [21] from the anterior chest walls of ten subjects with proper guidance/assistance of a general physician. Consent regarding the collection of data from the subjects is taken before the recordings. The HSs

Figure 3: The recorded heart sound signal

signals are recorded in mono audio format at a sampling

frequency of 16 kHz, for approximately 10 seconds ($x \in \mathbb{R}^{16000 \times 10}$ or $x \in \mathbb{R}^{160000}$) by placing the said MEMS microphone at the left fourth intercostal space of the patient's chest, the recorded PCG sample is shown in Fig. 3.

2.2. Additive and Convolutional Noise

In the case of cardiac auscultation, additive noise mainly includes respiratory sounds and environmental noise. The

Figure 4: Parametric model of the PCG signal acquisition process showing additive noise and convolutional distortion.

convolutional distortion represents the transduction effect of the stethoscope sensor. The schematic model of the stethoscope given in the previous section can also be shown in Fig. 4. Therefore, for a given short time segment of length N , the additive convolution phenomenon can be expressed as Eq. 1.

$$x[t] = (e[t] + n[t]) * h[t] \quad (1)$$

Here, PCG, noisy PCG, additive noise and stethoscope impulse response are given by, $e[t]$, $x[t]$, $n[t]$ and $h[t]$, respectively.

The captured HS signal from the previous section with all the additive convolution noise as seen in Fig. 3, can also be expressed as Eq. 1. This signal is then split into short-time frames of 500 ms or 8000 samples ($x_i \in \mathbb{R}^{16000 \times 500 \times 10^{-3}}$ or $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^{8000}$) by passing it through a Hanning window (Eq. 2) [22] with a frame-over lap of 10 ms or 160 samples ($x_i \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{16000-8000}{16 \times 10^3 \times 10 \times 10^{-3}}}$ or $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^{950}$).

$$w[t] = 0.54 - 0.46 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{N-1}\right) \quad (2)$$

Where, $w[t]$ is the windowing function and $0 \leq t \leq N-1$, N is the window length. The rationale behind this step is that as frequencies in a signal change over time so in most cases it does not make sense to process the entire signal, in doing so the minute frequency contours of the signal are lost over time. Therefore, the effective dimension of the input audio signal after this step is $x \in \mathbb{R}^{8000 \times 950}$.

2.3. Feature extraction pipeline

This section presents the signal processing pipeline for audio feature extraction as illustrated in Fig. 5. The feature extraction pipeline described here can be broadly divided into three stages, each of which is assigned to perform a particular function. The first stage simply acts as a data acquisition system bringing the PCG audio over. The second stage is where the majority of the signal processing happens, the stage starts with a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) block followed by a power spectra extractor. The extracted

Figure 5: The feature extraction pipeline for heart sound recognition

power spectra are passed through a bank of specialized filters (i.e. Mel filter) beyond which the log and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) blocks yield three audio features in stage three. The signal processing and relevant mathematical explanation from stage two are given in the succeeding sections.

2.3.1. Fourier-Transform and Power Spectrum

The first step in the extraction pipeline is taking a K -point DFT on each windowed frame of the captured HS thereby calculating the frequency spectrum, which is also called Short-Time Fourier-Transform (STFT) given by Eq. 3.

$$X[k] = (E[k] + N[k])H[k] \quad (3)$$

Where, $X[k]$, $E[k]$, $H[k]$, and $N[k]$ represent the DFT coefficients of the corresponding time domain signals for $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, K$ in the DFT operation (in Eq. 3) which mostly returns complex numbers, the power spectrum is estimated by squaring the absolute value of the DFT coefficients according to Eq. 4.

$$P[k] = \frac{|X[k]|^2}{N} \quad (4)$$

The calculated power spectrum operation from Eq. 3 is shown in Eq. 5.

$$|X[k]|^2 = (|E[k]|^2 + |N[k]|^2)|H[k]|^2 + 2 \operatorname{Re}(E[k]H[k]N[k]^*H[k]^*) \quad (5)$$

The last term of Eq. 5 can be regarded as negligible in this development as both $e(t)$ and $n(t)$ in the original Eq. 1 are statistically independent. Therefore, according to the said assumption Eq. 5 can be rewritten as Eq. 6.

$$|X[k]|^2 = (|E[k]|^2 + |N[k]|^2)|H[k]|^2 \quad (6)$$

2.3.2. Mel spaced Filter Banks

The power spectrum obtained from Eq. 6 is then passed through a set of triangular filter banks to obtain a Mel spectrum.

$$m = 2595 \times \log_{10} \left(1 + \frac{f}{700} \right) \quad (7)$$

The magnitude spectrum obtained is therefore warped according to the Mel scale which represents frequency resolution to properties of a human ear. The linear frequency

in Hertz (f) can be mapped to the Mel scale (m) as per the following Eq. 7 [23]. The triangular filter bank can be obtained according to Eq. 8 [24].

$$H(m, k) = \begin{cases} 0 & k < f(m-1) \\ \frac{k-f(m-1)}{f(m)-f(m-1)} & f(m-1) \leq k \leq f(m) \\ \frac{f(m+1)-k}{f(m+1)-f(m)} & f(m) \leq k \leq f(m+1) \\ 0 & k > f(m+1) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Where, m is the number of filters required and $f(m-1)$ generates a list of $m+2$ Mel spaced frequencies as given by Eq. 9 [25].

$$f(m) = 700 \times \{10^{(\frac{m}{2595})} - 1\} \quad (9)$$

Therefore, considering a set of predefined m filters the i^{th} filter can be energy shown as Eq. 10. At each frequency, the product of $|X[k]|^2$ (from Eq. 6) and filters $H(m, k)$ is calculated, the overall product can also be written as Eq. 10.

$$|X[i]|^2 = \mathbb{F}_k^i(|X[k]|^2) \quad (10)$$

Where, \mathbb{F}_k^i denotes the i^{th} filter operation on the k frequency sample. The overall filter response given by Eq. 11 can be obtained from Eq. 6 and Eq. 10.

$$|X[i]|^2 = (|E[i]|^2 + |N[i]|^2)|H[i]|^2 \quad (11)$$

In Eq. 11 $E[i]$, $N[i]$ and $H[i]$ are the filterbank-energy values obtained from the corresponding DFT coefficients. It can also be seen from Eq. 11 that in the filter bank energy domain the background noise $N[i]$ is additive whereas the impulse response of the recording element $H[i]$ is multiplicative to the heart sound signal $E[i]$.

2.3.3. Log of Mel Filter Energy (LMFE)

To calculate the log of filter bank energies, a logarithm operation is performed on the energy coefficients obtained from Eq. 11.

$$\log(|X[i]|^2) = \log(|E[i]|^2 + |N[i]|^2) + \log(|H[i]|^2) \quad (12)$$

The logarithm operation given in Eq. 12 can also be rewritten as Eq. 13

$$L_X = L_{(E+N)} + L_H \quad (13)$$

Where, L_X , $L_{(E+N)}$ and L_H represent the vector of m elements generated by the application of Mel filters from the previous section. Therefore, with the log analysis on the Mel filter energy (from Eq. 11) it can be inferred that the captured PCG signal $E[i]$ continues to have the noise component $N[i]$ whereas, the convolutional distortion due to the recording media has now become additive in nature.

Table 1

The extracted features for 150 frames of the audio signal

Name	Description	Dimension
MFE	Filterbank energy features as shown in Eq. 11	(26, 150)
log-MFE	Log-filterbank energy features as shown in Eq. 12	(26, 150)
MFCC	After DCT compression as shown in Eq. 14	(26, 150)

2.3.4. Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs)

The final step in the feature extraction pipeline is the generation of the Mel frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) [26] by applying Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) on Eq. 13

$$DCT[L_X] = DCT[L_{(E+N)}] + DCT[L_H] \quad (14)$$

Where, $DCT[L_X]$, $DCT[L_{(E+N)}]$ and $DCT[L_H]$ represent DCT operation on the LMFE signal values that are obtained from Eq. 13. Since the log of filter bank coefficients computed in the previous step are highly correlated as seen by Eq. 12. Therefore, DCT is used to decorrelate the filter bank coefficients and yield a compressed representation of the filter banks.

Figure 6: The extracted a) Mel filter energy, b) log of Mel filter energy and c) MFCC features

2.4. Description of collected features

The previous sections show extraction of three different varieties of filter-bank based acoustic features from the PCG signal. These features are extracted using a signal processing pipeline shown in Fig. 5. The features are extracted for 150 frames of the PCG signal using each step described in the previous section, the feature dimensions are summarized in Table. 1. The extracted Mel Filter Energy (MFE) according

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to Eq. 11 for 150 frames of the PCG signal using 26 Mel filters is shown in Fig. 6a and the log of the extracted MFE feature is shown in Fig. 6b. Finally, the DCT compressed signal is shown in Fig. 6c.

3. Experimental implementation

3.1. Implemented Classifier

A CNN is primarily used for image classification, however; in many 1D signal processing applications, 2D spectrogram images can be used as input features to a CNN model for classification [27, 28]. In this work, a 1D-CNN is used instead of a 2D-CNN to process the extracted features due to hardware constraints and computational efficiency, treating each row of the spectrogram as a separate feature. This approach optimizes memory usage and captures sequential patterns in the audio data while accommodating the limited resources of microcontrollers [29]. Hence, a 1D-CNN is used here as a classification model, the architecture of the network is shown in Fig. 7. The classifier has two Convolution layers with kernel size 3 each having Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation. The extracted 2D spectrogram (shape 26×150 from Table. 1) feature matrix is flattened (shape 1×3900) after which it is ingested by the convolution layer. The first convolution block has a kernel size of 3 and is followed by a Maxpooling layer having a pool stride value of 2. The second convolution block has a kernel size of 3 and is also followed by a Maxpooling layer of stride value 2, both the convolution blocks have a Dropout layer with a drop out probability of 0.25 in between. The output from the second convolution block is then flattened after a Dropout layer (dropout probability of 0.25) and fed to a fully connected neural network having softmax activation for binary classification between normal and abnormal PCG signals. The model is implemented using TensorFlow-Keras [30, 31] framework.

Figure 7: The CNN model architecture for heart sound abnormality detection.

The TensorFlow-Keras model from the previous section is then saved and transferred into corresponding FlatBuffer using TensorFlow Lite (TFLite) interpreter after a Post-Training Quantization (PTQ) [32] procedure. The two different quantization levels chosen for this implementation are *float32* and *int8*.

3.2. Training and performance considerations

The 2016 PhysioNet/CinC Challenge database [12] includes 3,157 recordings from 764 patients. It consists of

Table 2
PhysioNet/CinC Challenge Database data distribution.

Subsets	Subject	Recordings		Device used
		Normal	Abnormal	
a	121	117	292	Welch Allyn Meditron
b	106	385	104	3M Littmann E4000
c	31	7	24	AUDIOSCOPE
d	38	27	28	Infral Corp.Prototype
e (Normal.)	174	1867	0	MLT201/Piezo
e (Abnormal.)	3351	0	151	3M Littmann
f	112	80	34	JABES

84,425 cardiac cycles with heart rates ranging from 35 to 159 bpm. The PCG recordings come from seven research groups (a-g, i). Table. 2 provides an overview of this dataset. Notably, six of the categories (a-f) are publicly available for training, with durations between 5 and 120 seconds. Additionally, the PASCAL 2011 Heart Sound dataset [13] comprises 832 audio clips obtained from the general population in a noisy hospital environment using an iPhone app and a digital stethoscope. The clips range in length from one to thirty seconds and is divided into two sections. The first set (Dataset A), contains 432 audio clips obtained from the general public via an iPhone app, and the second set (Dataset B), consist of 400 audio samples recorded with a digital stethoscope in a loud hospital environment. To create the training data set, an equal number of recordings classified as *normal* and *murmur* are selected from two sources: the 'e' subset of the PhysioNet/CinC Challenge database (which used a heart microphone [33] similar to the one used in this study), and the PASCAL database. Additionally, a percentage of locally gathered recordings, as mentioned in section 2.1, are included in the data set. The distribution of recordings in the training data set is illustrated in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: The distribution of heart sound files in the training data set.

The network shown in Fig. 7 is trained on 486 wav files where 70% of the data is kept for training, 20% for validation and 10% of the rest is used for testing to prevent overfitting [34]. The loss function for the network is Categorical Crossentropy and the learning rate for the optimiser Adam is kept at 0.002 after a couple of varied attempts so that the network converges in a reasonable amount of time. Post the training procedure, the said network is tested on 49 (i.e. 22 murmur and 27 normal) unseen heart sound recordings. The classification event is shown in Fig. 9 in the form of three

Figure 9: Confusion matrix of classification for extracted a) MFCC, b)log-MFE and c) MFE features

confusion matrices for each extracted feature fed to the 1D-CNN. To evaluate the network performance the following metrics described in the succeeding sections are calculated.

3.2.1. Accuracy

Accuracy is defined as Eq. 15, it is evaluated to check how comfortable the proposed model is in detecting the positive and negative class of heart sound.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (15)$$

According to the confusion matrices from Fig. 9, the overall accuracy of the classifier with MFCC as input feature is 93.8%, with log-MFE is 77.5% and with MFE is 63.2%.

3.2.2. F-score

To assess the binary classifier's propensity towards false positives and negatives, the F-score is calculated according to Eq. 16.

$$\text{F-score} = \frac{TP}{TP + \frac{1}{2}(FP + FN)} \quad (16)$$

The gathered F-score for each feature input is 93.8% for MFCC, 77.5% for log-MFE and 63.1% for MFE.

3.2.3. Precision

The precision score is calculated according to Eq. 17 to measure the ability of the classifier to correctly identify positive cases from all the predicted positive cases.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (17)$$

The precision score for the classifier fed with the MFCC feature is 92.8%, the log-MFE feature is 71.4% and the MFE feature is 63.6%.

Table 3

Performance comparison between TensorFlow-Keras and TFLite exported 1D-CNN for extracted features

S No	Metric	MFCC		log-MFE		MFE	
		Keras	TFLite	Keras	TFLite	Keras	TFLite
1	Accuracy	0.938	0.912	0.775	0.753	0.632	0.614
2	Precision	0.938	0.912	0.775	0.753	0.631	0.613
3	F-score	0.928	0.902	0.714	0.694	0.636	0.618
4	YI	0.872	0.847	0.543	0.527	0.263	0.254
5	DP	3.065	2.980	1.346	1.308	0.601	0.584

3.2.4. Youden's Index

Initially proposed in [35], Youden's Index (δ) is a way for benchmarking the performance of a diagnostic test, the value of δ usually ranges between 0 and 1 (both inclusive). The validity of a diagnostic test is given by the nearness of the δ value to 1. The Youden's Index is given by Eq. 18

$$\delta = \text{sensitivity} - (1 - \text{specificity}) \quad (18)$$

Where sensitivity = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$ and specificity = $\frac{TN}{FP+TN}$. The Youden's Index (YI) value for the classifier fed with MFCC is 0.872, log-MFE is 0.543 and that of MFE is 0.263.

3.2.5. Discriminant Power

The metric Discriminant Power (DP) [36] is used to evaluate the ability of the classifier to distinguish between positive and negative examples. The algorithm is a poor discriminant if $DP < 1$, limited if $DP < 2$, fair if $DP < 3$, and good in other cases. The DP value is calculated according to Eq. 19.

$$\text{Discriminant Power} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{\pi} (\log X + \log Y) \quad (19)$$

Where $X = \frac{\text{sensitivity}}{1-\text{sensitivity}}$ and $Y = \frac{\text{specificity}}{1-\text{specificity}}$. The DP value of the classifier when fed with the MFCC feature is 3.065, the log-MFE feature is 1.346 and 0.601 when fed with MFE values. Therefore, it can be observed that the classifier significantly underperforms when fed with MFE feature data compared to log-MFE and MFCC. The metrics from the TFLite exported classifier for each feature are listed above in Table. 3. Here, it can be seen that TFLite model compared to the standard TensorFlow-Keras model suffers from a degradation in overall efficiency by about 3% [37] when Table. 3 is compared with section 3.2.1, 3.2.2, 3.2.3, 3.2.4 and 3.2.5. As a final step, a hex dump of the saved TFLite model is generated for a microcontroller to be able to interpret it.

3.3. Model performance and optimization

The choice of implementation is taken to ARM Cortex-M [38] microcontrollers that are supported by the popular Arduino programming language framework [39]. The benefit of using the Arduino programming language is, it significantly reduces the development time because of the presence of pre-written libraries. The ARM Cortex-M boards used here in this work are, Raspberry Pi Pico [40], Arduino

Table 4

The microcontroller boards considered in this work

S No.	Feature	Microcontroller board type		
		Raspberry Pi Pico	Arduino Nano 33 Ble	Teensy 4.0
1	Processor	RP 2040	nRF52840	MIMXRT1062
2	Architecture	Cortex M0+	Cortex M4	Cortex M7
3	Clock (MHz)	133	64	600
4	Flash (MB)	2	1	2
5	SRAM (KB)	256	256	1024
6	SIMD	No	Yes	Yes

Table 5

Variation of inference time and current draw with microcontroller architecture type

S No.	Device	Cortex type	Clock (MHz)	Time (ms)	Current (mA)
1	Raspberry Pi Pico	M0+	133	53.8	38.3
2	Arduino Nano 33 Ble	M4	64	28.5	8.6
3	Teensy 4.0	M7	600	1.6	16.8

Table 6

Variation in latency for optimized model

S No.	Board type	Latency (ms)		Improvement (%)
		float32	int8	
1	Raspberry Pi Pico	53.87	45.30	15.90
2	Arduino Nano 33 BLE	24.38	23.19	5.13
3	Teensy 4.0	1.64	1.59	3.04

Nano 33 Ble [41] and Teensy 4.0 [42] with the last two having dedicated hardware Single Instruction/Multiple Data (SIMD) unit like ARM DSP to accelerate DNNs, details on each of the microcontrollers are given in Table. 4. The saved heart sound classifier model from the previous section is then furnished with any one type of (i.e. MFCC or log-MFE or MFE) feature and the on-device inference time is recorded, this test is performed on the three development boards results from which are shown in Table. 5. It can be seen from Table. 5 that the entry-level Cortex M0+ clocked at 133 MHz has the largest inference time of around 53.87 ms, whereas the Cortex M4 based Arduino Nano 33 BLE has an inference time of about 24.38 ms and the Cortex M7 based Teensy 4.0 reports an inference of 1.64 ms. Thus, *latency* or amount of time taken to run a single inference with a given model is lowest for the Cortex M7 based Teensy 4.0 board because this is one of the flagship commercial high-performance microcontrollers. However, the entry-level Cortex M4/M0+ microcontroller shows a significant amount of latency at 24.38 and 53.87 ms, respectively. To decrease latency a fully quantized (int8) model is considered. In this, integer quantization of both weight and activation values are performed, the quantization of the model helps by (i) relying on integer-only arithmetic for microcontrollers that lack hardware DSP engines, (ii) reducing the memory footprint of coefficient parameters and (iii) not leading to accuracy degradation on target microcontroller [43]. The variation in latency for the optimized *int8* model over the *float32* is given by Table. 6, it can be observed that the Cortex M0+ based Raspberry

Pi Pico benefits from the quantization showing about a 15-16 % decrease in latency. However, the other two boards with Cortex M4/M7 microcontrollers do not experience that significant decrease in latency; because they are already benefiting from a dedicated DSP (as seen from Table. 4). So, even with the int8 optimization and higher core clock of 133 MHz, the Cortex M0+ microcontroller is not able to come anywhere near the latency values of the Cortex M4 based board (core clock 64 MHz) reported even with the unoptimized float32 model. The feature extraction pipeline from section 2.3 is replicated for the said microcontroller boards using ARM's CMSIS-DSP wrapper [44].

3.4. Implementation of the auscultation device

The choice of the microcontroller for the portable implementation comes down to these two factors i.e. performance and overall power consumption. The Cortex M4 board draws 28.38 mW (at 3.3 v \times 8.6 mA from Table. 5) of power when considered for a mobile application. The portable implementation is shown in Fig. 10, which uses the said Cortex M4 based microcontroller in conjunction with the said MEMS microphone as seen in Fig. 10a. The PCG

Figure 10: The prototype of the developed stethoscope with a) top side embedded system and b) bottom side power management

signals picked up by the MEMS microphone are directly read by the onboard Analog-to-Digital converter (ADC) of the microcontroller and are delivered to the DSP pipeline via the Direct Memory Access (DMA) buffer. The top half of the implementation also has a TDA2822M [45] based audio amplifier with adjustable gain for directly listening to the PCG signals. The bottom half shown in Fig. 10b, has a 240 mA at 3.3 v Li-ion battery to power the whole system and a DC-DC boost converter to power the TDA2822M. The classification result is indicated by a programmable (pin 22, 23, 24) Red-Green-Blue (RGB) light emitting diode (LED) present on the said Arduino board with red for murmur and green for normal. The developed prototype consumes around 20.71 mA (peak) of current as seen from Table. 7 while running inference, this when considered with the Li-ion battery can provide a continuous operation time of 11.5 hours.

Table 7

Peak power draw (at 3.3 v) for the developed prototype

S No.	Device parts	Current (mA)		Power (mW)
		Idle	Peak	
1	Arduino Nano 33 BLE	7.8	8.6	68.34
2	TDA 2822M		12	
3	MEMS microphone	0.075	0.11	

Table 8

The total time taken by the DSP pipeline on each microcontroller type

S No.	ARM arch. type	Core Clock (MHz)	Latency (ms)		
			MFCC	log-MFE	MFE
1	Cortex M0+	133	1213.96	1119.23	1047.22
2	Cortex M4	64	618.26	606.31	591.18
3	Cortex M7	600	121.23	117.76	115.36

Table 9

Device performance in different environmental conditions

S No	Metric	MFCC		log-MFE		MFE	
		40 dB	60 dB	40 dB	60 dB	40 dB	60 dB
1	Accuracy	0.892	0.863	0.697	0.673	0.491	0.422
2	Precision	0.892	0.863	0.697	0.673	0.491	0.422
3	F-score	0.881	0.843	0.631	0.592	0.511	0.479
4	YI	0.787	0.716	0.496	0.432	0.211	0.192
5	DP	2.612	2.411	1.112	1.012	0.523	0.373

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. On device performance

The implemented device is shown in Fig. 10, to select the right input feature the time taken by the DSP pipeline to extract each feature is considered, given in Table. 8. Taking a particular architecture type it can be seen from Table. 8 that the microcontroller takes the most amount of time in extracting the MFCC feature. On the other hand extraction of the MFE feature takes the least amount of time irrespective of the microcontroller architecture as seen in Table. 8. The MFE feature on the Cortex M0+ takes 13.73% less time compared to MFCC and about 5% less time on the Cortex M4/M7 microcontroller. However, it can be noted from Table. 3 that classification network performs poorly when fed with MFE feature, because of the presence of the highly correlated noise as pointed out in Eq. 11. Since, reliability of the detection and the amount of time taken; both are important it can be said taking Table. 3 and 8 into account that the log-MFE feature can produce dependable results at decent latency values. Environmental noise plays an important part (as mentioned in section 2.2) in deciding the detection efficiency of the implemented system shown in Fig. 10. Therefore, the prototype was taken for testing in two different environmental conditions i.e. Home (40 dB noise floor) and a busy clinic (60 dB noise floor); the efficiency metrics are shown in Table. 9. It can be observed from Table. 9 when compared with Table. 3 that all three features suffer due to background noise, with about 2%-10% decrease across the board. The fall in performance also increases with the increase in noise level. However, MFCC

Table 10
Comparison with similar heart sound classification techniques

S No	Framework	Detection							Peak power consumption
		Features	Model architecture	Device architecture	Implemented on	Peak Accuracy	Inference time	Portability	
1	This work	MFCC	1D-CNN	ARM	Cortex M0+	91.2 %	45.30 ms	Yes	166.35 mW
					Cortex M4		23.19 ms		
2	Suyi Li et. al.	Time-frequency	1D-CNN with GRU	x86/amd64	Cortex M7	95.5 %	1.6 ms	Yes	95.40 mW
3	Umair Riaz et. al.	Time	KNN		Cortex A76		5 ms		
4	Mishra et. al.	MFCC	CNN with stacked auto-encoder	x86/amd64	Cortex A53	99.80 %	Did not mention	Yes	10 W
5	M Deng et. al.	MFCC	CRNN		Intel Core i5		Did not mention		No
					Intel Core i5	98.34 %	1.2/0.9s	No	300 W

suffers the least (about 2% when 40 dB and 5.3% when 60 dB noise) compared to the other two feature sets. The classification performance hence comes down to 1D-CNN's ability in making out the right features from the noisy signal.

4.2. Microcontroller-feature combination

The combination of the microcontroller and extracted feature, therefore, boils down to two aspects. The first one is the floor for minimum allowable latency and the second is the overall cost of the system to achieve the mentioned level of latency. The Cortex M0+ based Raspberry Pi Pico is the cheapest of the lot at \$4 [40]. However, it struggles to produce respectable numbers when it comes to running inference (both with and without *int8* optimization as seen from Table. 6 and Table. 5) or the DSP pipeline (from Table. 8) even though it is clocked at a core frequency of 133 MHz. On the other hand, the Cortex M4 based Arduino Nano 33 BLE (core clock 64 MHz) produces decent performance numbers (from Table. 5 and Table. 8) while consuming much less power (68.34 mW). These performance numbers benefit from the fact that the Cortex M4 microcontroller has hardware floating point accelerators which do come at a cost, around \$21.45 (removing the cost of all the sensors the Arduino board has) [41]. The Cortex M7 is a flagship microcontroller that shines across the performance board, supported by the 600 MHz core clock. Similarly, in the case of extracted features, MFCC for the given classification network type produces the highest DP and accuracy values (seen from Table. 3) and is also much less susceptible to noise (Table. 9). However, the latency in gathering this particular feature is highest when compared to MFE and log-MFE. The log-MFE on the other hand has decent performance when it comes to DP and accuracy values over the MFE feature for which the classification network performs poorly because of the correlated noise as explained before. The inexpensive Cortex M0+ board in combination with log-MFE can, therefore, be considered for MLSensor [46] applications where portability and cost are two important factors. The log-MFE feature can be considered in the solution, taking into account the DSP-pipeline latency value from Table 8, which represents the time it takes to extract this feature on a Cortex M4 based Arduino board. However, it is important to highlight that MFCC has a higher classification accuracy, as indicated in Table 3, albeit with a higher DSP-pipeline latency. Both MFCC and log-MFE provide DP values greater than one, indicating their potential usefulness for

the classification task. In the scenario where the developed device is used as a primary screening device, where the goal is simply to determine the presence or absence of the disease, log-MFE can be employed. This is because log-MFE, with lower latency, can provide a quick indication of disease presence. However, considering the significance of early disease diagnosis in the medical field, the implementation has chosen to prioritize MFCC. This implies that although MFCC incurs a higher latency in the DSP pipeline, it is preferred due to its higher classification accuracy. Early disease detection is crucial for timely medical intervention, and the accuracy of classification plays a vital role in achieving this objective. The decision to opt for MFCC over log-MFE in the implementation is based on the understanding that timely and accurate diagnosis outweighs the concern for latency.

4.3. Comparison with similar work

The developed HS auscultation apparatus is further assessed against a few related works that are considered to be state-of-the-art, as shown in Table. 10. The genuine state-of-the-art in HS classification has been revealed in [47] and [48]. The authors achieve near-perfect accuracy scores (i.e. 99.80 % and 98.3 %) by using much more complex classifier structures (i.e. autoencoder stacked 1D-CNN and a Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (CRNN)) than the simple 1D-CNN used in this work, which produces accuracy values of about 91.2 % (93.8 % when the unoptimised TenorFlow-Keras model is considered). However, it should be mentioned that the authors employed a desktop computer (64-bit Intel Core-i5 Microsoft Windows-10 PC) with a discrete graphics card (GeForce GTX 760/GTX 1080ti by Nvidia) to execute inference on the PCG data in both of these implementations. As a result, this consumes approximately 235-300 W of power, as opposed to the 68.34 mW (considering the Cortex M4 based Arduino) of the implementation technique used here. However efficient the above stated methods are, they lack in portability and overall power consumption. Similarly, the authors of [49] and [50] presented two portable HS classification frameworks that leverage Time-frequency features to achieve the same results. When compared to the MFCC feature fed 1D-CNN classification topology of this work, these provide near-ballpark accuracy results (i.e. 95.5 % and 94 %). However, the authors used an application profile [51] ARM processor in both of these implementations, as opposed to the microcontroller profile [52] processor used in this study. As a result, these two solutions consume more power (i.e. 15.5 and 10 W,

respectively) while providing comparable accuracy values. The referenced studies achieve higher accuracy scores using more complex classifiers or Time-frequency features, they rely on powerful desktop computers or application profile ARM processors, resulting in higher power consumption and reduced portability. In contrast, the current work employs a simpler 1D-CNN classifier with MFCC features, running on a microcontroller profile processor, leading to lower power consumption, much lower inference latency i.e 1.6 ms (when ARM Cortex M7 based Teensy 4.0 board is considered) and enhanced portability, albeit with slightly lower accuracy. The choice of approach depends on the trade-off between accuracy, power consumption, and portability requirements for the specific HS classification application.

5. Conclusion

This article presents a detailed examination of a portable device for near real-time heart sound classification, utilizing a microcontroller. The study encompasses an analysis of the effects of additive noise and convolutional distortion on collected PCG signals. Three feature vectors, namely MFCC, log-MFE, and MFE, are extracted from the PCG signals and employed to train a 1D-CNN model. The trained network is evaluated using five performance metrics, as shown in Table. 3, revealing that the MFCC features consistently outperform the other feature vectors in all categories. The obtained results are particularly noteworthy when compared to related state-of-the-art works. While other studies achieve near-perfect accuracy scores with more complex classifiers or time-frequency features, they rely on powerful desktop computers or application profile ARM processors, resulting in higher power consumption and reduced portability. In contrast, the proposed microcontroller-based implementation demonstrates commendable accuracy, achieving approximately 91.2% accuracy using a simpler 1D-CNN classifier with MFCC features. This approach offers the advantage of low power consumption, consuming only 68.34 mW. Despite slightly lower accuracy compared to the state-of-the-art approaches, the portability and overall power efficiency of the microcontroller-based solution are significant advantages, particularly in scenarios where early disease detection and mobile, on-the-go healthcare are crucial. Furthermore, the study confirms that the utilization of well-designed features, such as MFCC, effectively maintains resilience against noise and sensor degradation, thus enhancing the reliability of heart sound classification tasks. In conclusion, the developed microcontroller based portable device, leveraging MFCC features, showcases its suitability for near real-time heart sound classification. The solution achieves commendable accuracy while offering portability, low power consumption, and robustness against noise and sensor variations.

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